

BEHAVIOR OF SHAPE MEMORY ALLOY ACTUATORS EMBEDDED IN COMPOSITES

**C. Liang
C. A. Rogers
Smart Materials & Structures Laboratory
Department of Mechanical Engineering
Virginia Polytechnic Institute and State University
Blacksburg, Va 24061, U.S.A.**

ABSTRACT

Shape memory alloy fibers, and in particular Nitinol fibers, embedded in composite materials as distributed actuators have been demonstrated to have numerous control capabilities. Many new control concepts have been conceived based on the unusual behavior and unique control parameters available from Nitinol fiber actuators. This paper presents a model to describe the recovery stress and recovery strain relationships and behavior that is unique to shape memory alloys. Based on this model, a fundamental constitutive relationship for SMA-actuators is developed by assuming a transversely orthotropic material with an initial stress. This basic constitutive model is then implemented into a finite element analysis to demonstrate the mechanical behavior of the SMA distributed actuator fibers embedded in a matrix material.

INTRODUCTION

Shape memory alloy reinforced composites is a class of materials that have the ability to change their material properties, induce large internal stresses in the fiber actuators, which can modify the stress and strain distribution of the structure, and alter its configuration, all in a controlled fashion. The unique mechanical behavior of the SMA laminates also introduces some new characteristics in the formulation, solution and results of classical plate problems. It is through these special characteristics and behavior that active modal modification, active strain energy tuning, buckling control, and acoustic transmission control can be implemented (1).

Using shape memory alloys as fiber reinforcement gives structures numerous adaptive capabilities. Adaptive and/or smart materials, which contain distributed actuators, sensors, and microprocessor capabilities, can be used in many applications requiring a high degree of adaptability to changing external and internal conditions. External conditions may consist of environment, loads, or the desire to change the scope, purpose, or geometry of the structure after it has been built and is in service. Internal conditions may be damage or failure to isolated portions of the material or structure.

The ability to adaptively alter the mission, scope, objectives, and geometry of a structure will have tremendous impact on the design philosophy of structures in the future. For example, a structural member made of shape memory alloy (SMA) reinforced composites can compensate for deterioration in absorptivity and thermal expansion properties that result in excessive change in length of that or other members as well as control the motion and vibration of the structure. The same material can be used to change load paths in a structure or within the material so that the component can be replaced or repaired before it causes catastrophic failure of the system or unacceptable degradation of performance.

The development and subsequent production of this class of materials could have a significant impact on several diverse technological fields, i.e., material science, vibrations and controls, ocean and

aerospace structures, biotechnology, and may act as a catalyst for the development of many new devices and technologies. Brief descriptions of some the applications and the corresponding basic operational modes of the shape memory alloy reinforced composites appear in Ref. (2).

1. Introduction to Shape Memory Alloys

The shape-memory effect (SME) can be described very basically as follows: an object in the low-temperature martensitic condition, when plastically deformed and the external stresses removed will regain its original (memory) shape when heated. The process, or phenomenon, is the result of the reverse transformation of the deformed martensitic phase to the higher temperature austenite phase. The solid-solid phase transformation also yields other useful characteristics such as the ability to control the material properties such as Young's modulus and the yield strength reversibly and reliably.

Many materials are known to exhibit the shape memory effect. They include the copper alloy systems of Cu-Zn, Cu-Zn-Al, Cu-Zn-Ga, Cu-Zn-Sn, Cu-Zn-Si, Cu-Al-Ni, Cu-Au-Zn, Cu-Sn, and the alloys of Au-Cd, Ni-Al, Fe-Pt, and others. The most common of the shape memory alloys or transformation metals is a nickel-titanium alloy known as Nitinol. Nitinol is the SMA of choice for use as an embedded distributed actuator because of its unusually high resistivity which allows for resistive heating.

Nickel-titanium alloys (Nitinol, NiTi) of proper composition exhibit unique mechanical "memory" or restoration force characteristics and the characteristics of changing the material properties reversibly. The shape recovery performance of Nitinol is phenomenal. The material can be plastically deformed in its low-temperature martensite phase and then restored to the original configuration or shape by heating it above the characteristic transition temperature. This unusual behavior is limited to NiTi alloys having near-equiatomic composition. Plastic strains of typically six-to-eight percent may be completely recovered by heating the material so as to transform it to its austenite phase. Figures 1 and 2 show the nonlinear mechanical properties as a function of temperature and the unique restoring stress characteristic of shape memory alloys (3). It can be seen that the Young's modulus of Nitinol can increase by three times and the 0.2 percent yield strength increases from about 83 MPa to about 620 MPa; the recovery stress, which is the stress caused by the restoration tendency for the fully rigid restraint case, changes as a function of temperature and initial strain.

Figure 1. Yield Stress and Elastic Modulus vs. Temperature

Figure 2. Restoring Stress vs. Temperature for Nitinol

2. Shape Memory Alloy Reinforced Composites

The class of the material referred to as SMA reinforced composites in this paper is simply a composite material that contains shape memory alloy fibers (or films) in such a way that the material can be stiffened or controlled by the addition of heat. One of the many possible configurations of the SMA reinforced composite material is one in which the shape memory alloy fibers are plastically elongated before embedding and constrained from contracting to their 'normal' or 'memorized' length upon curing the composite material with high-temperature. The plastically deformed fibers are therefore an integral part of the composite material and the structure. When the fibers are heated, generally by passing a current through the shape memory alloy fibers, the fibers 'try' to contract to their 'normal' or 'memorized' length and therefore generate a internal stress field. To whole composite, this could produce a predictable inplane force and moment which can be used to active control the dynamic and static response of the composite.

To actively control the response of the SMA reinforced composites, we can either 'tune' the mechanical properties of the embedded actuator fibers or impart large internal restoring stresses throughout the structure which is known as active strain energy tuning ([4] and [5]). Tuning the mechanical properties, also known as active modal modification, means that the SMA fibers or films are embedded without being plastically deformed, i.e. no shape memory, and changing temperature 'tunes' the overall stiffness of the composite. Therefore, we can modify the response of the structure and avoid introducing large internal loads and stresses in the structure. Active strain energy tuning is accomplished with SMA fibers (or actuators) that are embedded with a certain amount of initial strain. Once the fibers are actuated, the overall stiffness of the structure changes and an internal force, restoring stress, is created because of the SME allowing control of various control parameters of the structure.

CONSTITUTIVE RELATION OF SMA ACTUATOR

A large amount of research has been reported on the mechanical and physical properties of SMAs and Nitinol in particular. Reference (3) gives a general review of the mechanical and physical property characterization studies that have been performed on Nitinol. However, most of the published literature is focused on common mechanical behavior. It is well known that the material is extremely rate and path sensitive, including both rate of activation and strain rate. In order to reliably use Nitinol as an actuator for vibration, acoustic and damage control, new and more complete mechanical characterization studies are needed.

There is still a great deal that can be learned about the fundamental behavior of SMA reinforced composites and some of the problems that may be encountered by using the currently available characterization literature. However, presently we are investigating the restoring stress vs. restoring strain characteristics with an experimental apparatus that resembles a simplified SMA actuator fiber - composite 'matrix' model. A SMA fiber actuator when embedded in a composite 'matrix' and activated will tend to contract to its 'memorized' contracted length. However, the composite 'matrix' material provides a constraint which limits the amount of recovery strain possible. It is this relationship between the activation temperature of the fiber, hence the recovery stress, and the recovery strain as a result of the elastic constraint that is not well understood. In order to quantify this characteristic of Nitinol we have created an experimental apparatus that consists of a SMA actuator fiber and a tensile spring in series. By using different springs and varying the activation temperatures we can get a relation of recovery stress vs. recovery strain which yields the basic 'constitutive' relationship of the actuators.

To determine the overall mechanical properties of the SMA reinforced composite a model was formulated and described in Ref. (6). The model allowed for calculating the [A], [B] and [D] matrices while incorporating the change in Young's modulus and the inplane force caused by the SME. The formulation assumed the rule of mixtures and it is also assumed that the inplane force caused by the contraction of the SMA fibers is uniformly distributed. In experimental studies we have demonstrated that a composite beam made of Nitinol/Graphite-Epoxy can be activated and controlled to reversibly increase the natural frequency by 20 percent. This composite beam contained approximately five percent Nitinol in volume fraction with five percent initial strain. The initial investigations show that SMA reinforced composites have great potential for deformation control, vibration control, buckling control and acoustic control (6). However, several potential problems are also obvious such as the strength of the structure after activation of the SMA fibers and the integrity of the actuator/'matrix' interface which could lead to possible delamination. These problems can be addressed by funda-

mentally studying a single fiber embedded in a matrix. To do this, the recovery stress-strain relation which we have referred to as the 'constitutive' relation must be determined first.

1. Constitutive Relation of Recovery Stress and Strain

Using the experimental apparatus described above we are able to actuate a Nitinol fiber that has been initially plastically strained and attached to tension springs of varying spring-rates to determine the recovery stress-strain relation. As shown in Fig. 3, the relationship between the recovery stress and the recovery strain is not linear, but it can be linearize in a piecewise fashion. For small strains, believed to be less than 0.5 percent, which is much greater than the strain of the actuator fibers embedded in the matrix, we can use an approximate linear relation: For large strains, which often occur at the free edge, the recovery stress-strain relation is simply a different linear range.

For small strains, let \bar{E} be the tangential value of the first linear range and $\bar{\sigma}_r$ be the recovery stress when the wire is rigidly restrained. The subscript r denotes recovery terms. The linearized recovery stress-strain relation can be expressed as:

$$\sigma_r = \bar{\sigma}_r + \bar{E}\epsilon_r \quad [1]$$

Note that \bar{E} is not the Young's modulus but rather a tangent modulus of the shape memory effect: The recovery strain ϵ_r is a negative quantity. If an external stress is applied during the recovery or SME process, the actuator stress is:

$$\sigma = \sigma_r + E\epsilon_{tc} \quad [2]$$

Where E is the elastic Young's modulus and ϵ_{tc} is the tension or compressive strain. Superposition between the common stress and the recovery stress is assumed.

2. 3-D Recovery Stress-Strain Model For SMA Fiber Actuator

Considering a SMA fiber embedded in a 'matrix' material, let the z-direction be the fiber direction, the x-y plane be the transverse plane of the fiber, and assume the 3-D stress-strain (including the recovery stress and strain) relation to be transversely orthotropic. For small strains, since the recovery stress strain relation is approximately linear, we can derive the stress-strain relationship in a similar manner as to considering elastic transversely orthotropic materials.

It is assumed that the z-direction stress-strain relation is governed by Eqs. [1] and [2], and the x-y plane stress strain relation is linear-elastic. Replacing the x-y-z notation with 1-2-3, the strain-stress relationship for a SMA-actuator can be expressed in matrix form as:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \epsilon_1 \\ \epsilon_2 \\ \epsilon_3 \\ \epsilon_{23} \\ \epsilon_{13} \\ \epsilon_{12} \end{bmatrix} = \begin{bmatrix} \frac{1}{E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{21}}{E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_{33}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{12}}{E_{11}} & \frac{1}{E_{22}} & -\frac{\nu_{32}}{E_{33}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ -\frac{\nu_{13}}{E_{11}} & -\frac{\nu_{23}}{E_{22}} & \frac{1}{E_{33}} & 0 & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{23}} & 0 & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{13}} & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & 0 & \frac{1}{G_{12}} \end{bmatrix} \begin{bmatrix} \sigma_1 \\ \sigma_2 \\ \sigma_3 - \bar{\sigma}_r \\ \sigma_{23} \\ \sigma_{13} \\ \sigma_{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad [3]$$

Where E_{33} is the tangent modulus, \bar{E} . Considering our initial assumptions, we still have the following relations.

$$\begin{aligned}
 E_{11} &= E_{22} \\
 G_{13} &= G_{23} \\
 \nu_{13} &= \nu_{23} \\
 \nu_{31} &= \nu_{32} \\
 \nu_{12} &= \nu_{21}
 \end{aligned}
 \tag{4}$$

To keep the the compliance matrix symmetric and positive definite, we have:

$$\frac{\nu_{31}}{E_{33}} = \frac{\nu_{13}}{E_{11}}
 \tag{5}$$

The same relations hold for ν_{32} and the other like terms. In fact, for SMA fibers with five percent initial strain which is in the range of plasticity, we could assume the ν_{13} and ν_{12} to be 1/2. We do this also because the σ_{33} term is the most important in the analysis. For the same reason, it is also assumed that G_{13} is equal to the G_{12} and that results in:

$$\nu_{31} = 0.5 \frac{E_{33}}{E_{11}}
 \tag{6}$$

$$G_{13} = G_{23} = G_{12} = \frac{E_{11}}{3}
 \tag{7}$$

The implication of Eq. [6] is that ν_{31} is very small because E_{11} is usually tens times greater than E_{33} . Inverting the compliance matrix results in the stress-strain relation in the compact matrix form.

$$[\sigma] = [S_{ij}]^{-1}[\epsilon] + [\bar{\sigma}]
 \tag{8}$$

Where $\{S_{ij}\}$ and $\{\epsilon\}$ are the compliance and strain matrices of Eq. [3], The $\{\sigma\}$ is $\{\sigma_1 \sigma_2 \sigma_3 \sigma_{23} \sigma_{13} \sigma_{12}\}^T$ and $\{\bar{\sigma}\}$ is $\{0 \ 0 \ \bar{\sigma} \ 0 \ 0 \ 0\}^T$.

In this model we have simplified the 3-D SMA fiber actuator stress-strain relation to a transversely orthotropic elastic problem with an initial stress in z direction for small strains.

Figure 3. Recovery Stress-Strain Relation

Figure 4. Composite Cylinder Model

FINITE ELEMENT ANALYSIS

For SMA reinforced composites, using the composite cylinders model shown in Fig. 4, with a known actuator fiber volume fraction and radius of the actuator fibers denoted by a , we can find the equivalent radius b of the cylinder with one fiber embedded. If the actuator fiber volume fraction is α then the a and b has the following relation:

$$b = \frac{a}{\sqrt{\alpha}} \quad [9]$$

1. Finite Element Formulation

In our finite element analysis we only consider the stress caused by the shape recovery effect and assuming that there is no other external load and the thermal stress is neglected. Equilibrium for an fiber element expressed with conventional notation is:

$$\{F\}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \{B\}^T \{\sigma\}^e dv \quad [10]$$

Substituting Eq. [8] into Eq. [9], we have:

$$\{K\}^e \{\delta\}^e = \{F\}^e - \{\bar{F}\}^e \quad [11]$$

Where

$$\{K\}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \{B\}^T \{S_{ij}\}^{-1} \{B\} dv \quad [12]$$

$$\{\bar{F}\}^e = \int_{\Omega^e} \{B\}^T \{\bar{\sigma}\} dv \quad [13]$$

In our problem, $\{F\}^e$ is zero. The only load considered is caused by the shape memory recovery effect. Solving this finite element equation, we can get the stress distribution and displacement field.

2. Finite Element Results

The stresses and their distribution caused by the shape memory effect of the embedded actuator fibers are shown in Figs. 5 and 6. It is interesting to note that where the stresses in the fiber drop sharply at the free edge, the matrix stresses (near the fiber) increases rapidly. In fact, the strains at the free-edge of the structure are so large that they would be in the range of plasticity for which the current linear-elastic calculations can only give qualitative indications of the effect of SMA fiber actuators embedded in the material. Away from the free-edge (greater than five times the radius of the fiber), the stresses remain relatively constant. Figure 6 shows the normal stress, σ_x , of the SMA actuator fiber and matrix constituents changes with the radius. For an actuator fiber volume fraction of 5 percent, resulting in b/a of about 4.5, the normal stress σ_x is essentially uniformly distributed throughout the matrix. For a free-free boundary condition, there should be a self-equilibrium at any transverse cross-section. For fixed boundary conditions, the resultant force for any transverse section is the recovery force of the fiber and the resultant force is independent of the material properties. It is also evident that the stresses (mainly the shear stress between the fiber and matrix) away from the free-edge is so small that we may conclude that the integrity of the interface between the actuator fiber and the matrix is generally assured.

However, it is equally clear that reinforcement will be needed to maintain the structural integrity demonstrated away from the edge. At the free edge where there is a large stress and strain concentration, accurate prediction of the state of stress and strain is a relatively complicated problem requiring large strain, plasticity and thermal stress capabilities.

Figure 5. Z-Direction Stress

Figure 6. R-Direction Stress

CONCLUSION

SMA reinforced composites have demonstrated tremendous potential for use in the future. This paper presented a fundamental investigation of the recovery stress-strain relationship which is needed for reliable and responsible development of this class of adaptive materials. This fundamental micromechanic investigation illustrated the difficulty of modeling, solving and most importantly, predicting a-priori the behavior of this most peculiar class of materials. The extremely small stresses transferred from the actuator to the matrix as shown in this paper is a significant discovery and will be further investigated analytically as well as experimentally. Large strain and plasticity nonlinear effects will be added to the current model to better predict the behavior of the material system at the free-edge.

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